

Low-Symmetry Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Complexes

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Active interest in the complex chemistry of oxo-vanadium (IV) during the last few years is very well reflected in the appearance of a review article in 1965¹ which was followed within a year by a supplementary review article². Since the proposal of two orbital splitting models of the 3d¹ oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes initiated by Ballhausen and Gray³ on the one hand and a second cluster level model by Ortolano, Selbin, and McGlynn⁴ on the other, much activity is being demonstrated in the absorption spectral studies⁵⁻⁹ of its coordination complexes. It is now believed that both these models might be used suitably in order to explain the spectral behaviour of the complexes. Whereas most of the complexes provide spectra at room temperature in conformity^{7,8,9} with the Ballhausen-Gray model, a few low symmetry complexes of oxo-vanadium (IV) with such ligands as tartaric acid, malic acid, mandelic acid etc. furnish as many as four absorption bands⁵ in the ligand field region as demanded by the second model. Some support to the latter scheme was also obtained from a recent report of some mixed ligand chelates of oxo-vanadium(IV)⁶.

Our interest in low symmetry oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes is indicated in the report of diaquo lutidinato oxo-vanadium (IV) hydrate⁷ and several mixed chelates^{10,11} arising out of the combination of any of the several tridentate, dibasic ligands pyridine^{5,6} dicarboxylic acids, iminodiacetic acids with any of the bidentate ligands, oxalic acid, glycine, acetylacetonate, κ - κ' dipyrridyl, o-phenanthroline etc.

The report of Sacconi and Campigli⁶ concerning mixed chelates with tridentate, monobasic Schiff bases and a bidentate, monobasic hydroxyaldehyde prompts us to report some preliminary results of our own studies on a broad group of low symmetry oxo-vanadium(IV) mixed chelates arising out of the combination of tridentate, dibasic Schiff bases and another strong field ligand, κ - κ' dipyrridyl or o-phenanthroline.

Complexes of series 'A' contain such tridentate ligands as resulting from combination of any of the bidentate salicylaldehyde, resoroylaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde

1. Selbin, *Chem. Revs.* 1965, 65, 153.
2. Selbin, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1966, 1, 293.
3. Ballhausen and Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.
4. Ortolano, Selbin and McGlynn, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 41, 262.
5. Selbin and Morpurgo, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 673.
6. Sacconi and Campigli, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 606.
7. Dutta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, 273.
8. Dutta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, 290.
9. Dutta and Syamal, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, 361.
10. Dutta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, 296.
11. Dutta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, 306.

with any of the bidentates, glycine, α -alanine, anthranilic acid. Complexes of the series 'B' contain acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde, resorcyaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde in combination with benzoylhydrazide or salicylhydrazide. Both these two groups of tridentate ligands were forced to combine with oxo-vanadium (IV) and then the resulting complexes further made to react with *o*-phenanthroline or α - α' dipyridyl.

All these complexes have dark colours, chocolate to red, are non-electrolytes and all provide paramagnetic values. These are generally soluble in chloroform and pyridine.

Complexes of series 'A' provide comparable absorption bands both in chloroform and pyridine solvents, though mostly two absorption bands around 17,000-18,000 cm^{-1} and a very broad one 13,000-14,000 cm^{-1} are exhibited. The similar nature of the two absorption bands presumably indicate octahedral stereochemistry of the complexes and non-coordination of pyridine. However, complexes of series 'B' show remarkable difference in their absorption spectra in the two solvents. The chloroform spectra reveal at most one absorption band in the ligand field region whereas the pyridine spectra in most cases exhibit at least three sharp absorption bands and sometimes even four throughout the ligand field region. Some of these low symmetry complexes, thus shows splitting of the degenerate levels in the Ballhausen-Gray Scheme, and support the O S M Scheme. Besides, the marked difference in the pyridine spectra compared to the chloroform one stands for pyridine coordination. It is however a point for speculation as to whether the complexes are octahedral or 5-coordinated in the solid state. This probably can only be settled through an X-ray investigation. Spectral and other properties of five of the thirty such complexes so far studied are included in the Table.

TABLE I
Oxo-Vanadium (IV) mixed chelates

Complex	Colour	Analyses		Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Absorption Bands (cm^{-1})
		Found	Calculated		
1. [VO(dipy) (Hydroxynaphthaldehyde-anthranil)]	Brown	V: 10.08 N: 8.2	9.92 8.17	1.82	(a) 17,000-17,100; 12,800-13,900 (b) 17,000-17,100; 12,800-13,900
2. [VO(dipy) (Salicylaldehyde-anthranil)]	Chocolate	V: 10.64 N: 8.88	10.9 9.03	1.60	(a) 18,200-18,500; 12,000-14,500 (b) 18,200-18,500; 12,000-14,500
3. [VO(dipy) (Salicylaldehyde-benzoylhydrazide)]	Chocolate red	V: 10.88 N: 11.88	11.01 12.09	1.83	(a) 13,300-14,100 (b) 17,900-18,500; 16 700; 15, 600-15,200; 11,600-11,000
4 [VO (<i>o</i> -phen) (Hydroxynaphthaldehyde-salicylhydrazide)]	Dark brown	V: 9.2 N: 9.95	9.2 10.1	1.83	(a) No peak (b) 15,500-15,400; 14,300-13,000 12,800-11,500,
5 [VO(dipy) (Salicylhydrazide-acetylacetonone)]	Orange	V: 11.11 N: 11.99	11.13 12.2	1.71	(a) 14,500-13,200 (b) 18,500-18,200; 17,300-17,000; 16,100, 14,900-14,700
6. [VO(Hydroxynaphthaldehyde-anil)]	Green yellow	V: 9.18 N: 5.08	9.09 4.89	1.54	(a) 19,200-18,200; 16,400-13,900 13,200-12,800 (b) 17,500-17,200; 14,300-13,300

(a) in chloroform and (b) in pyridine

Besides these low-symmetry complexes, several C_{2v} symmetry oxo-vanadium (IV) bidentate Schiff base complexes have also been prepared following standard procedures^{12,13} and their spectra recorded in chloroform and pyridine. These reveal some expected difference in absorption bands arising out of pyridine coordination. The table records the spectra of one such complex.

We have also begun to study the reactions of bis hydroxyaldehyde (say salicylaldehyde) oxo-vanadium (IV) with excess of aromatic amines (say aniline). These studies have so far indicated the formation of bis hydroxyaldimine oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes with no indication of further coordination of the aromatic amine so as to make the complex octahedral. The identity of these reaction products have been checked by direct synthesis using the hydroxyaldimines concerned and comparing the analyses, decomposition temperatures and visible absorption spectra in different solvents.

We will report the full details of our above studies on completion of the elaborately conceived scheme.

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12. Pfeiffer, Hesse, Pätzner, Scholl and Thielert, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1937, 149, 217.

13. Pfeiffer, Thielert, and Glaser, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, 132, 145.